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**GENDER DYNAMICS IN BOLLYWOOD;
FEMINIST PERSPECTIVE ON “QUEEN”**

ABSTRACT

There has been an ongoing argument amongst various scholars regarding the portrayal of women in Indian cinema. Women are often depicted as objects of the male gaze or are trivialized and marginalized completely. As a result, they are limited to gender-stereotypical roles such as those of a caring, loving wife or an obedient daughter whose main purpose in life is to prioritize other's needs and happiness over hers, especially the male figure. “Bollywood has a long history of preserving conservative cultural and ideological notions regarding women's sexuality while negotiating the demands of social and political-economic progress. As a result, the "new" women in Bollywood have evolved during the last few decades.” (Ahad and Akgül) This paper will examine "*Queen*," a gripping Bollywood film directed by Vikas Bahl, from a feminist theoretical and popular culture perspective, using theories like *symbolic annihilation of women, patriarchy, and psychoanalysis*.

The movie “Queen” centres around a young woman Rani Mehra who is engaged to be married but her fiancé dumps her shortly before the wedding. Rani feeling very lost and heartbroken, decides to go to Europe on her honeymoon alone. Through this journey, she realizes her self-worth, discovers her voice and enthusiasm for life; and embraces her newfound independence. Ultimately, she comes back stronger, ready to face any challenges that life throws at her.

“Feminism in Popular Culture studies how mainstream media, entertainment, and popular culture promote, share, and value feminist ideas, ideals, and representations.” (Holland, Samantha. *Feminist Review*, no. 88, 2008, pp.) Feminist theory is a useful framework for examining "Queen" since it explores gender dynamics, stereotypical norms placed on women, power dynamics, and societal expectations—all of which are major issues not only in the movie but also in our society as a whole. The study of how mainstream media portrays upholds, and challenges *patriarchal* views is made possible by the intersection of feminism and mass culture. Using a feminist lens to analyze this film allows us to question if the movie addresses or contributes to the *symbolic annihilation* of women in popular culture. Furthermore, analyzing the characters' motivations and inner conflicts in more depth is made possible by incorporating *psychoanalytic theory* into the investigation. This paper aims to examine the ways in which this film is portrayed in popular culture, to gain a deeper understanding of how it reflects and influences larger cultural attitudes and perspectives.

KEY TERMS DEFINED:

- Symbolic Annihilation of Women: According to Tuchman, “*The term symbolic annihilation of women describes how women and their concerns are ignored, marginalized, excluded, or trivialized in cultural output and media depictions.*” (Strinati) In the movie “Queen” we will analyze the transformation of the protagonist Rani from embodying stereotypical gender roles to ultimately challenging these representations.
- Patriarchy: “*The power relations that allow men to dominate and oppress women are commonly referred to as patriarchy.*” (Beechey, V. (1979) In the context of the movie “Queen”, we will look at how patriarchy affects the characters and their behavior; how they are expected to act according to the societal norms and the expectations placed upon them by society.
- Psychoanalysis: “*A technique for investigating the mind and how it functions, especially through behavior, dreams, and emotions.*” (“Psychoanalysis | Definition, Theory, and Therapy”) In "Queen," psychoanalysis could be utilized to comprehend how gender norms and societal standards impact the characters' psyche and actions (Rani as well as her family).

IN-DEPTH ANALYSIS:

1. Symbolic Annihilation of Women

In the context of "Queen," the way the protagonist Rani is first portrayed exhibits symbolic Annihilation. The opening scene introduces the audience to a Big fat North-Indian wedding and presents Rani as the embodiment of traditional womanhood. "Rani is shown as a devoted and polite bride-to-be, influenced by cultural expectations and rituals surrounding marriage and womanhood, through interactions with her family and her inner monologue during her mehendi ceremony."(Menon) She faithfully prepares for her wedding and puts her family's needs and expectations first, which depicts traditional gender norms and the underrepresentation of women's empowerment and autonomy in popular culture. *For instance*, consider the following dialogues:

Dialogue 1- Rani's mother: *"You have to realize that it's not just about you at your wedding. The honor and reputation of our family are at stake. You must take every measure to ensure that the wedding goes smoothly."*

Rani: *"What about what I want, Ma? Isn't it important that I am happy too?"*

Rani's mother: *"Of course, it matters, but sometimes we have to sacrifice our desires for the sake of our family."*

In this conversation, Rani's mother highlights how Rani is expected by society to put her family's reputation before her happiness. Since Rani's freedom and wishes are subordinated to maintaining patriarchal customs and norms, this debate represents the symbolic annihilation of

women. This reflects how women are often treated in our society; they are expected to prioritize other people's needs especially those of their family above themselves. Rani's battle to assert herself highlights a larger problem in society, where women must strive against these unjust expectations. "Women seem to be caught in a never-ending cycle of marginalization and being told that gratifying other people's needs comes before their satisfaction."(Sharma)

Dialogue 2- Rani's fiancé: *"I feel we shouldn't get married, I don't think we are fit for each other. I have completely changed, but you are still the same Rani; Our lifestyles don't match anymore."*

Rani replied: *"But what about my dreams, my future?"*

Rani's fiancé: *"Your dreams? You're future? Rani, stop being so absurd. Your future was always supposed to be with me, encouraging my aspirations."*

The outdated idea that women are solely there to assist men's ambitions is reinforced in this interaction when Rani's fiancé brushes off her goals and dreams. It emphasizes the symbolic annihilation of women's interests and autonomy in partnerships by trivializing Rani's desires and goals. This shows how he belittles Rani's desires and aspirations, indicative of a deeply embedded gender hierarchy where women are expected to perform subordinated roles and their own goals are viewed as secondary to those of males.

These dialogues from the movie "Queen" show how the movie depicts women as being symbolically misrepresented and undermined by societal norms, dismissive attitudes, and the marginalization of women's autonomy and wants.

The movie also criticizes how marriage has become a commodity and how women are under pressure to fit in with society's expectations. This critique is closely related to the idea of the symbolic annihilation of women; it exposes how women's identities and experiences are marginalized and devalued within patriarchal structures. In this society, women may be viewed more as objects or as means of enhancing a person's wealth or position. *For instance*, this notion is called into question by Rani's journey; after learning that her wedding is called off, she begins to wonder if marriage defines a woman's value. She embarks on a journey where she defies gender norms and exposes the injustice of expecting women to conform to specific roles based only on their gender. The film primarily emphasizes Rani's refusal to fit in with society's unjust expectations of women.

2. **Patriarchy (Gender norms and societal expectations)**

The way Rani's family and friends initially responded to her broken engagement is blatantly patriarchal. They consider her trip unusual and reckless, and they see her as incomplete in the absence of a spouse. The deeply held patriarchal notion that a woman's value is dependent on her marital status is reflected in this response. Their disapproval of Rani's choice to travel alone serves to further reinforce the stereotype that women ought to put their relationships with men before their independence and autonomy. This is evident in the dialogue between Rani and her family.

Rani: *"But why should I go alone? What will people say?"*

Family Member: *"It's embarrassing. How can you go on a honeymoon alone?"*

This dialogue highlights Rani's initial reluctance to go against societal norms and go on this trip by herself. The pressure she faces from her family to adhere to conventional gender norms is also portrayed in this conversation. Ideally, society expects women to be heartbroken and sad if she is dumped right before their wedding; instead, Rani defies these norms and embraces her freedom, she looks at it as an opportunity to break free from the conventional norms and live her life. She believes that her life does not have to depend on a mere man, she can live and enjoy her life independently. So her family and relatives, representing the 'society' itself find it odd that she is going on her honeymoon alone. Rani is put under pressure not only by her close friends and family but also by her external relatives (whom she meets on her trip to Paris) who maintain patriarchal standards.

Rani's aunt: *"Independence? It is not the behavior of respectable Indian girls. Instead of seeing the world by yourself, you should be married and submit to your spouse. What will your parents say about this? Later don't come crying to us."*

The relative's mocking and disrespectful attitude towards Rani's choice to go alone in Paris is perfectly captured in this conversation. The relative still questions Rani's decisions and undermines her self-confidence, despite her claims of independence and self-sufficiency. This dialogue demonstrates how Rani has to deal with gender norms and cultural constraints while traveling.

Furthermore, Rani's interactions with males while traveling demonstrate how prevalent patriarchal attitudes and actions—from harassment to arrogance—are. She encounters male strangers who belittle and doubt her because she is a woman and they question her capacity to travel alone. *For example*, when she tries to check into her hotel in Paris, the receptionist seems

surprised and a little unsure that she is traveling alone. The patriarchal notion that women are essentially weak and in need of male protection is reinforced by this exchange, which reflects the social norm that women shouldn't travel to new places alone. To further emphasize the widespread prevalence of gender-based violence and objectification, Rani also encounters harassment and unwanted advances from men. *For instance*, Rani feels uneasy and insecure when she comes across a group of males when visiting Amsterdam because they make offensive remarks and lewd gestures towards her. Through this encounter, the film highlights how women often have to go through gender-based violence; just because she was traveling alone, without any male companion she was subjected to such gestures by a group of males. This is often seen in patriarchal societies where women become victims of such objectification and violence.

3. **Psychoanalysis**

In the movie psychoanalysis can be used to understand the thought processes, behavior, and intentions of characters other than Rani, providing insight into how societal conventions and gender roles influence these individuals' mindsets and actions *For example*, Rani's mother might act in ways that are a result of her internalization of patriarchal standards, including putting the family's reputation ahead of Rani's happiness. Similarly, Rani's father's reaction to her called-off wedding would have been motivated by his insecurities and anxieties about being judged and expected by society. This shows how their upbringing and socialization have shaped their perspectives on gender roles and expectations. Furthermore, we can examine how cultural expectations and pressures might have influenced Vijay's (ex-fiance) decisions and behavior through his words and actions. He states that living abroad had changed him completely as a person as well as his thought process, whereas Rani on the other hand living in India was the

same conservative person. He didn't think their lifestyles matched anymore, and demeaned Rani by saying that she wouldn't be able to adjust to "his world". He may have been afraid of the social repercussions and wanted to live up to the expectations of success and manhood in society, which is why he abruptly called off the wedding.

This theory also helps in examining Rani's journey, especially concerning her irrational fears and wants. She was traumatized by her broken engagement and societal expectations, which suppressed her subconscious yearning for independence and self-discovery, which is why she decided to go on the solo trip. Rani is driven to leave her comfortable surroundings and explore the unknown, despite the cultural norms and the pain of her broken engagement. Through her journey, her deepest hopes and wishes are symbolically explored.

Furthermore, Rani's interactions with Vijaylakshmi in Paris might be understood as igniting her personal empowerment and self-discovery path. In contrast to Rani's prior encounters, Vijaylakshmi embodies independence, spontaneity, and confidence. She might represent Rani's unconscious aspirations for freedom and self-determination. "Rani starts to unlock these hidden desires in herself by interacting with Vijaylakshmi and seizing the opportunities she presents."(Ray) This can be seen when Rani decides to dance freely on the street, expressing herself which earlier she wasn't given the freedom to by her ex-fiance.

Vijaylakshmi: *"Rani, get moving! Let's teach the residents of these areas the art of dancing!"*

Rani: *"But what if people stare?"*

Vijaylakshmi: *"Who gives a damn? We should dance as if no one is around."*

Rani: *"You're correct (with a smile). Let's get started!"*

This conversation demonstrates how Vijaylakshmi's influence on Rani has transformed her. She helps Rani accept and embrace her independence, and overcome social restraints with her courage and support, opening the door for happy moments, self-realization, and individual empowerment.

Towards the end of the movie, a significant moment for Rani is her confrontation with Vijay in Paris. It seems as though she is asserting her independence and declaring, *"I, not you or anyone else, am in charge of my life."* Initially, Rani might have thought that she had to live up to Vijay's expectations of her; however, she learns that she is no longer bound by those regulations in Paris. This demonstrates her growing capacity for self-confidence and independent thought. Rani is addressing certain uncertainties and fears within herself by confronting Vijay; she understands now that no one else but herself is in charge of her life. She won't listen to him and go back, simply because he is reconsidering his marriage with her and begging her to come back to his life. This portrays Rani's significant progress towards growing stronger and more self-assured.

CONCLUSION:

After examining "Queen," it is clear that the movie delivers more than just a story; it delves deeply into themes of identity, empowerment, and social criticism. The story questions established gender standards and invites viewers to reevaluate society's expectations by looking at it through the prism of feminist thought. Reclaiming one's agency and authenticity can be a great source of strength and resilience; Rani's journey from a confined individual to a liberated woman is a remarkable example of this. As she fights against stereotypes and claims her worth and independence, she finally subverts conventional expectations and challenges the idea of symbolic annihilation. Furthermore, the movie makes viewers reconsider the widespread effects of patriarchy and the value of self-discovery in overcoming repressive structures. Viewers are encouraged to embrace their agency, challenge social norms, and enjoy the power of self-realization as Rani's path is revealed. Essentially, the movie "Queen" proves to be an influential story that not only amuses audiences but also questions their preconceptions about identity, agency, and freedom.

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